

Quarrying Cult at Simitthus (Chemtou, Tunisia)

By David Wallace-Hare, University of Exeter

Entry tags: Cave Shrines, Nature Sanctuaries, Landscape features, Religious Place, Landscape, Roman State Religions, North Africa, Industrial Site (religiously affected), Roman Religious Traditions, Religious Group, Ancient Mediterranean, Animist, Roman Private Religions

The entry focuses on the religious activities of a group of imperial freedman procurators in their management of the marble quarries at Simitthus, a city in the Roman province of Africa Proconsularis, in active operation as imperial property beginning in the second half of the second century CE to the mid third century. The marble quarry, which formed the economic backbone of the city of Simitthus, is also a site where the boundaries of public and private religion blur as the procurators and their staff utilized local deities to control risks associated with extractive operations through targeted on-site deployment of deities connected to or made to connect to extraction operations. This entry strictly examines a period from 64 CE - 211 CE when the religious activities of these extraction officials are epigraphically attested (largely our only way to understand the religious dynamics at this site. The use of deities connected with industrial operations, in particular in imperial mining districts, has several analogues from other contemporary extractive operations, such as in the provinces of Dalmatia and Aquitania. The on the job utilization of certain types of local and agricultural deities, like Tellus and Terra Mater, and deities connected with mountains, is seen across several mining districts and seems to represent a reflex of Roman religious practices connected with the aversion of risk, especially agricultural risk, from economic operations. In engaging in these behaviours and moving around different mining districts, it is likely that a sort of orthopraxy for dealing with unseen risks accreted around certain deities like Terra Mater and Tellus, and created avenues for estimating what sorts of deities would be most efficient to seek out in unfamiliar areas (mountains). The religious feelings of the slave workforce, housed in a barracks-like structure to the northwest of the town, are little known. The marble quarrying zone, roughly 0.4 km in extent, occupies a zone comprising three hills at the heart of the city more or less. The quarrying zone is demarcated by a low wall that separates the town from the quarry. The quarry is bounded on one side by the river Bagradas, which allowed for the transport of the special yellow marble produced in the area, known to scholars as giallo antico.

Date Range: 150 BCE - 299 CE

Region: Simitthus (Chemtou, Tunisia)

Region tags: Africa, Northern Africa, Tunisia

Site of the town of Simitthus, which came to be a prime marble (yellow marble) extraction zone in the early Roman Empire.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Gasparini, V. 2021. "Urban religion and risk management at Simitthus (Chemtou, Tunisia)." In M. Patzelt, J. Rüpke, and A. Weissenrieder (eds.), *Prayer and the Ancient City Influences of Urban Space*. Tübingen. 133-160.
- Source 2: Khanoussi, M. 1998. "Les officiales marmorum numidicorum," in M. Khanoussi, P. Ruggieri, and C. Vismara (eds.), *L'Africa romana. Atti del XII convegno di studio*. Olbia, 12-15 dicembre 1996. Sassari. 997-1016.
- Source 3: Khanoussi, M. 2018. "Cultes et lieux dans les carrières antiques de marbre numidique de Chimtou (Tunisie)." In F. Baratte, V. Brouquier-Reddé, and E. Rocca. Paris (eds.), *Du culte aux sanctuaires: l'architecture religieuse dans l'Afrique romaine et byzantine: actes du colloque*, 18-19 avril 2013, Paris, Fondation Simone et Cino del Duca. Paris. 267-275.

Notes: Gasparini 2021 is the most comprehensive and newest treatment of the topic of industrial religion at Simitthus. It adopts a risk management framework to understanding the careful deployment of theonyms in the naming of specific workshops.

- Source 1: Dušanić, S. 1999. "The Miners' Cults in Illyricum," *Revue d'études antiques* 50: 129-139.
- Source 2: Fabre J.-M. and L. Fabre. 2014. "Les ex-[v]otos, les [s]cories et [!]a [m]ontagne," in E. Boube, A. Bouet, and F. Colleoni (eds.), *De Rome à Lugdunum des Convènes: Itinéraire d'un pyrénéen par monts et par vaux. Hommages offerts à Robert Sablayrolles*. Bordeaux. 333-338.
- Source 3: Mrozek, S. 1982. "Zur Religion der römischen Bergleute in der Prinzipatzeit," *Eos* 70: 139-148.

Notes: Associated relevant references on mining cult in the Roman Empire. Gasparini focuses on Simitthus alone in his account of risk management religion in the quarrying activities at Simitthus. The situation at Simitthus is not unique, however, and we find several similar cases of mining and quarrying religion among the upper level personnel (as in the case of some Dacian mining districts especially) and among craftsmen and potentially quarriers in southern Pyrenean Aquitania. Source 1 treats Dacian mining religion and forms a useful jumping off point to that topic. Sources 2-3 concern the Aquitanian evidence.

- Source 1: Beyrie, A., J.-M. Fabre, and R. Sablayrolles. 2000. "Les hommes de fer du dieu "Ageio": Exploitation antique du fer dans les Hautes Baronnies (Hautes-Pyrénées)," *Gallia* 57: 37- 52.

Notes: Associated relevant references on mining cult in the Roman Empire.

- Source 1: Hirt, A. 2010. *Imperial Mines and Quarries in the Roman World Organizational Aspects 27 BC-AD 235*. Oxford. 25-27.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://pleiades.stoa.org/places/318615>
- Source 1 Description: Coordinates of the marble quarry at Simitthus and associated bibliography.
- Source 1 URL: http://dx.doi.org.uoelibrary.idm.oclc.org/10.1163/1574-9347_bnp_e1113430
- Source 1 Description: Huß, Werner (Bamberg). 'Simitthus'. Brill's New Pauly. Ed. Hubert Cancik and et al. Brill Reference Online.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.dainst.blog/tana/simitthus-chimtou-2/>

– Source 1 Description: Simitthus/Chimtou. The city of the "numidian marble"

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1965-Present

Notes: Systematic excavations of Simitthus and its marble quarry began in the 60s and occurred in several phases. The first systematic phase (1965-1996) was undertaken jointly by the Tunisian Institute of National Heritage (INP) and the German Archaeological Institute of Rome (DAI). The second current systematic phase (2008-present), also joint between the DAI and INP is led by Philipp von Rummel and Moheddine Chaouali. On these systematic excavations, see the following outputs of these recent excavations: 1) Beschouch, A. et al., eds. 1993. *Simitthus I: Die Steinbrüche und die antike Stadt. Mainz am Rhein.* 2) Khanoussi, M. et al., eds. 1994. *Simitthus II: Der Tempelberg und das römische Lager. Mainz am Rhein.* 3) Mackensen, M., ed. 2005. *Simitthus III: Militärlager oder Marmorwerkstätten. Neue Untersuchungen im Ostbereich des Arbeits- und Steinbruchlagers von Simitthus/ Chemtou. Mainz am Rhein.* 4) Baldus, H. and M. Khanoussi, eds. 2014. *Simitthus IV: Der spätantike Münzschatz von Simitthus/Chimtou. Wiesbaden.* 5) Hess, U., K. Müller, and M. Khanoussi, eds. 2017. *Simitthus V: Die Brücke über die Majrada in Chimtou. Wiesbaden.*

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Simitthus I-V

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: Marble quarries

Notes: The religious group discussed in this entry, the upper level/ procuratorial mining personnel, are discussed in their relation to the marble quarries at Simitthus not their activities within the surrounding town (it is not a large town but the entry focuses on the industrial nature of their religious activities). The marble quarries are a feature of the landscape anthropogenically exploited. Marble extraction of the marmor Numidicum (a prized type of yellow marble produced in the area and linked to Numidia during the Roman period) focused on three hills to the NE of the town, known as the Gebel Chemtou collectively but to archaeologists as the Tempelberg, Stadtberg, and Gelberberg, occupying an area of 0.4 km. Marble extraction was the source of the town's economic growth. Most marble was exported with little used in the town proper. Procurators of the marble quarry seem sometimes to have named their workshops, according to recent work undertaken by V. Gasparini (2021), after certain deities to alleviate the risk of the expensive and physically demanding marble extraction processes. For example: AE 1994, 1861 (201 CE) (Chemtou / Simitthus, Africa proconsularis): N(umero) CCXXX[---]

of(ficina) Cael(estis) / Luciano et Fabi(a)no co(n)s(ulibus) / caesura Athenodo(ri) pro(curatoris) CIL VIII 14588 (183 CE)(Chemtou / Simitthus, Africa proconsularis): N(umero) CCCV of(ficina) Genii Montis / Imp(eratore) Commodus Aug(usto) IIII et Victorino [I]I co(n)s(ulibus) / caesura Maximi proc(uratoris) In both instances a procurator of an area of marble extraction, called a caesura, incision, is connected with a workshop named after a local deity, Caelestis in the first case, Gens Montis "spirit of the mountain" in the second. The second case shows a clear and obvious connection to quarrying work and the rationale behind calling the connected workshop for marble processing and managing after that deity. Similar processes are found in many areas of the empire. For example, at a marble quarry in the province of Asia, at Dokimeion, we find the following inscription: AE 1992, 1616 (198 CE)(Iscehisar / Dokimeion / Docimium, Asia): [Loc(o)] XI b(racchio) quart(o) com(missura) II Saturnino e(t) Gallo / co(n)s(ulibus) / [of]f(icina) Mar(tis?) caes(ura) Ulpi / (H)yacin(thi) Here the officina is named after Mars in what must amount to an analogous situation described by Gasparini. The work of quarrying was dangerous. A votive dedication set up by two quarrymen or more likely quarry managers, here not procurators, in southern Pyrenean Aquitania from roughly the same period as the preceding expresses thanks to two local deities, Sylvanus and Montes, over the safe extraction of marble columns: CIL XIII 38 = AE 1890, 96 (Marignac / Lugdunum Convenarum, Aquitania): Silvano deo et / Montibus Numidis / Q(uintus) Iul(ius) Iulianus et Publici(us) Crescentinus qui pri(mi) hinc columnas vice/narias claverunt et / {et} exportaverunt / v(otum) s(olverunt) l(ibentes) m(erito) The Montes here clearly parallel the gens Montis of the Simitthus workshop. Similarly, we see a group of marble workmen, officinatores, make a dedication, likely to a marble-connected deity in Aquitania, from the same region: AE 1949, 130 (Saint-Beat / Lugdunum Convenarum, Aquitania): Natalis Martialis / et Sintus of(f)icator(es) / cum suis col(l)egi(is) / v(otum) s(olverunt) l(ibentes) m(erito)

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Notes: Several workshops found at the quarry of Simitthus are connected with the quarry work and thus imbricated in the religious activities of the procuratorial staff managing the quarry (see Gasparini 2021).

Type of feature

–Other [specify]: zones of extraction (marble quarries)

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: The quarry and its workshops, are located in the NE section of the town and separated from it by a wall. It is clear the free quarry personnel and unfree are connected with the goings on of the connected city.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: No. Simitthus is in a heavily urbanized zone in the province of Africa proconsularis well-connected to riverine commerce, which allowed for the transportation of marble (this also occurred overland as well). Africa proconsularis was one of the most prosperous and urbanized of the empire.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: There were very few places in the ancient Mediterranean that were not or could not be imbued with religious identity in some way through the coopting of assistance from a variety of deities representing diverse functions (including economic functions). The quarry where the theophoric workshops were situated round, were economic and governmental (imperial controlled) spaces imbued with religious protections through deliberate naming. Votive dedications, mentioned elsewhere in this entry, could be used to control economic risk (the physical dangers of marble extraction and the fulfilment of quarried marble to its intended recipient(s)).

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Notes: There is a marble quarry and associated workshops. See Gasparini 2021 for an overview of the religious landscape connected with the quarry and its attached/connected structures.

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: It is a quarry with associated workshops

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: quarry

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

Notes: A quarry and workshops

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The quarry is part of the town.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Other [specify]: The feature (quarry) is economic in function but the workshops attached, officinae, are given theonyms sometimes to cut down on risk.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– No

Notes: The quarry and indeed the workshops are in perpetual states of change and constantly engaging with new risk to manage in the extraction process.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: various deities in the economic space and linked to the town, some are known from the epigraphic record via officinae names, others from votive dedications from the non-quarry areas of the town.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Several officinae are known, featuring different theonymic names, like the officina Caeslestis or officina gentis montis. There is no one single deity whose preserve the mines were. In other areas this is the case, too, as for example, in a votive dedication from southern Aquitania (Pyrenees)

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– King or emperor

– Other [specify]: The emperor charged his procuratorial staff (freedmen) with the oversight of the quarrying operations at Simitthus.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Slaves

– Men

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Material wealth

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

Notes: It is a site of marble extraction.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials
– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Notes: Rock reliefs are carved into the Tempelberg and seem an expression, perhaps by the quarry workers, of piety and may be connected with Saturn. See Hirt 2010: 25 and Kraus 1993.

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– Yes

↳ On the inside:
– No

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Identification of the specific god(s), is difficult. Kraus 1993 connects them with Saturn and suggests they are an expression of the popular veneration of Saturn.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Notes: They decorate the rockface of the Tempelberg on which a temple to Saturn was located.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– I don't know

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Not enough data to assess or indicate the primacy of a high god.

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: These are the deities of Simitthus, such as the gens montis, the spirit of the quarry essentially, mentioned in a workshop name: CIL VIII 14588 (183 CE)(Chemtou / Simitthus, Africa proconsularis): N(umero) CCCV of(ficina) Genii Montis / Imp(eratore) Commodo Aug(usto) IIII et Victorino [I]I co(n)s(ulibus) / caesura Maximi proc(uratoris) We see a similar deity in another marble extraction site in Pyrenean Aquitania: CIL XIII 38 = AE 1890, 96 (Marignac / Lugdunum Convenarum, Aquitania): Silvano deo et / Montibus Numidis / Q(uintus) Iul(ius) Iulianus et Publici/us Crescentinus qui pri(mi) hinc columnas vice/narias claverunt et / {et} exportaverunt / v(otum) s(olverunt) l(ibentes) m(erito)

↳ Human spirits can be seen:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: The use of votive dedications and the naming of workshops theophorically implies the presence of divine monitoring that can affect the outcome of economic actions in the extraction sphere.

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– I don't know

↳ In trance possession:
– No

↳ Through divination practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– No

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

↳ Other

- Other [specify]: Managing the risk/success of mining and quarrying operations (worker and operation protection)

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

- I don't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

- I don't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

- I don't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

- Yes

Notes: The use of votive dedications and the naming of workshops theophorically implies the presence of divine monitoring that can affect the outcome of economic actions in the extraction sphere.

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

- No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

- Yes

↳ Libations:

- Yes [specify]: Unknown

↳ Offerings of food:

- Yes [specify]: Unclear

↳ Animal sacrifice:

- I don't know

↳ Human sacrifice:

- No

↳ Sacred objects:

– I don't know

↳ Daily life objects:

– I don't know

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: The use of votive dedications at Simitthus suggests reciprocity relationships with local and imported deities similar to other areas of the empire.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: N/A

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

- ↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:
 - Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Within the context of the officina itself, it would not be surprising to learn that a shrine existed to safeguard the workers and procuratorial staff on a day-to-day basis. The naming of the workshops using theonyms provides a basis for such a suggestion.

- ↳ Are there animal sacrifices:
 - No

- ↳ Are there human sacrifices:
 - No

- ↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:
 - No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: On the Tempelberg, one of two main hills of the town adjacent the quarry, rock reliefs were found which are clearly votive in nature and represent offerings in this case. See Kraus, T. 1993. "Die Felsreliefs am Tempelberg." In A. Beschtaouch et al. (eds.), *Simitthus I: Die Steinbrüche und die antike Stadt. Mainz am Rhein.* 71-92.

- ↳ Are material offerings mandatory:
 - Yes

Notes: If votive in nature, they would be carved in fulfillment of a vow. They may have been expressions of a non-compulsory nature, a donum. They may not operate according to Roman religious vow procedures but could have been carved according to local practice.

- ↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– No

Notes: As marble was the source of life for the community in a sense, carving reliefs directly into the mountain may have been an explicit reference to this and thus would be made upon a valuable support.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: While rituals are difficult to document within the quarry itself and in its workshops, they must have occurred at important junctures that created new risk spaces or those that might affect the status qua/business as usual, each new juncture effectively representing a possible change to that business as usual. Consecrating a new quarry or gallery, for instance, would not be unexpected from what we know of Roman religion operating in imperially controlled industrial spaces.

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Yes (most likely), in the opening up of new sections of the quarry or at junctures where something goes wrong and results in life loss (to ensure non-repetition of the same event).

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Yes. Individual episodes of private religiosity which may have bordered on public likely occurred. See Gasparini 2021 for examples

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: unclear

Notes: Periodic celebrations of the emperor and his health or that of the imperial family were common throughout the empire. It is unlikely the festivals and celebrations would extend to the physical site of the quarries or the workshops. Certainly the opening of a new section of the quarry may have been attended by religious ritual, but this is not epigraphically attested at Simitthus.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: Where a procurator does not follow typical risk management procedures of naming a quarry workshop theophorically (less likely an orthopraxy area) or seeking the favour of quarry-connected deities in advance of or in response to risk (more likely to occasion comment from peers perhaps and supporting staff), we might see issues of orthopraxy enforcement or

comment. Nothing is preserved of this, however, but similar behaviours in other mining contexts where extractive deities, like Mater Terra (Dacia, Dalmatia, the Pannonias) are sought out by procuratorial staff especially, are indicative of such orthopraxy with respect to risk management strategies, an outgrowth of risk aversion strategies common from Roman agricultural practices, such as the Robigalia, no doubt (also because of the understanding of how minerals "grow" and are replaced underground is analogously understood via agricultural understandings).

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– I don't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Notes: Not exactly. The procurators who were in charge of the officinae, workshops, and marble quarrying operations at Simitthus, operated in religious ways by, for example, naming marble workshops with theophoric names, that can be found marking certain sections of the marble quarries called caesurae "incisions" (On caesurae and caesurae holders, see most recently Hirt 2010: 294-301, and 318-323. See also Fant 1989 and Drew-Bear 1994). According to Gasparini 2021, the deities selected by the quarry procurators in naming their workshops were selected sometimes because of their dual role as gods of the civic life of the community of Simitthus: "In this way they were able to place the (imperial) activity of the quarries under the protective umbrella of the same gods that the local civic community worshipped (i. e., a sort of attempt at institutionalization of a private venture), thus negotiating between 'civic' religion and 'lived' religion, that is, what we call here 'urban' religion." (Gasparini 2021:147)

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: In a manner of speaking. The procurators and likely many upon whom they delegated high authority in the quarries would have learned from one another how to manage risk religiously over many years of working the quarries to high levels of efficiency (getting the most out of their workforce involved both physical management of human resources, including slave management but also

perhaps hired labour, but also religious management of the risks of marble extraction through carefully cultivated relationships with local deities but also deities created for quarrying work or made to be related to that work, such as the gens montis utilized to name one of the quarry's workshops.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Notes: Not exactly. The quarrying site would have to be guarded and protected. Slaves employed in quarrying would have to be monitored in some cases. The quarrying site would have to be kept safe and structurally sound.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Notes: The procurator and his quarrying staff as well as non-free laborers in the quarries form a clear hierarchy.

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Notes: The bureaucracy would likely be permanent. Quarrying could occur year round.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: Simitthus is the site of an important marble quarry in operation for several centuries. Epigraphic and literary evidence of this exploitation begins in the second century CE. The quarry was under the control of the emperor, generally typical for marble quarries in the empire, until late antiquity when it seems to have been privatized or become open to private operators.

Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Notes: Yes. Marble clearly formed the economic backbone of Simitthus.

Does this place lease out land:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: According to Khanoussi, marble extraction continued as an imperial enterprise until the mid-3rd century CE when it seems to have become a private operation. For this to happen, some letting of sections of the quarry (as is common from other forms of Roman mining by conductores) likely occurred (Baldus and Khanoussi 2014: 10, see initial bibliography on this entry)

Does this place lease out tools:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Likely a variety of records (perishable in wax or on papyri) were kept in the officinae, workshops, of the marble quarry, especially given the fact that marble leaving marble quarries owned by the emperor was tracked and documented (we can see this in marked blocks mentioning caesurae holders). As economic spaces are also imbued with religiosity through risk management strategies involving coopting help from the gods, religious dedications are both sacred and secular by modern standards. Votive dedications mentioning mining deities at Simitthus or deities used as mining/quarrying deities, like Caelestis, are named in workshop names, such as the officina Caelestis, but also in votive dedications from Simitthus (Caelestis also had an official priesthood in the town): AE 1994, 1884 (Chemtou / Simitthus, Africa proconsularis): Caele{le}sti [---] / Primigenius Pontici Caesari[s --] / votum [solvit(?) ---]

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

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